

**Effects of Metacognitive Awareness on Senior High School Reading
Comprehension in English at Medina College Science High School**

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No known conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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ABSTRACT

This investigation aimed to find out the effects of metacognitive awareness of senior high school students' reading comprehension in English of Medina College Science High School during the school year 2018 – 2019. The descriptive survey method was used in answering the major problems and its corollary sub-problems. The proficiency levels of the male students on the metacognitive skills were found to be average in noting details in pictures, following printed directions, and getting the meaning of the paragraph. It was also found out that female students obtained above average on the following reading comprehension skills such as noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of phrases, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentences, getting the meaning of paragraphs, and sequence events as they happen. There is a significant difference between the male and the female students' proficiency level in metacognitive skills along noting details in pictures, getting the words, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentence, getting the meaning of paragraph, noting details in the selection, and sequencing events as they happen in the story. The male students' proficiency level was only average while the female students showed above average proficiency. The significant relationship between the metacognitive skills proficiency level and the scholastic performance profile of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students should be examined carefully by the teachers so that relevant provisions could be introduced for upgrading the students' proficiency levels on reading comprehension skills which would help improve and enrich students' scholastic performance profiles.

Keywords: metacognition in reading, metacognitive awareness, senior high school reading comprehension, students' metacognitive strategy, reading comprehension

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

Introduction

Metacognition is the capacity to look at how you handle thinking and feeling. This capacity enables students to recognize how they learn best. It also enables them to create self-awareness abilities that is imperative as they mature. Individuals who have created metacognition are able to survey their thought processes and reframe the way they think to adjust to different situations.

Using metacognition, students grasp an understanding of the circumstances, processes and strategies that work best for them. They may find that a method that works for one subject might require more time than another. Through the process of trial and error, students succeed in a few strategies and come up short in others while then attempting again.

Teachers can offer assistance to students by creating metacognition with a number of techniques. To begin, teachers can give students with knowledge on how the brain processes information, how it shapes information and memories, as well as the effect of stress has on these capacities. Teachers can moreover motivate students to recognize what they do not understand and examine how going up against the uncertainty as an indispensable process of the learning experience.

Students getting instruction on metacognition create abilities that will make them more effective in their academic and professional careers. The better able a student is to recognize how he or she learns, recollects and processes information, the more knowledge he or she will eventually retain. This capacity is also connected to building more better memory skills, which is an indicator of future academic success.

Dunlosky et al. (2013), clarify that students who recognize how they learn are more able to make circumstances that facilitate learning. For occasion, learners might know that they require to consider being in a calm room at a certain time of

the day or with note cards in a lesson that requires a more of memorizations. On the other hand, he or she might know that writing requires a distinctive sort of setting or time designation all together.

The significance of “learning to read” has invigorated significant debates—theoretical, practical, and political ones—about which teaching strategies and materials are the most optimal (Suggate et al, 2013). During the past ten years, debates have gotten to be more strident as calls for school accountability have increased.

The arguments on teaching reading are not theoretical, since teachers are progressively told by mandates what, how, and to whom to teach reading in their classrooms (Afflerbach et al., 2008). The arguments have moreover invigorated a more prominent dependence on logical proof by educational leaders and policymakers who need all teachers to utilize viable strategies and materials (Snow et al., 1998). Reading researchers, maybe presently more than ever before, have a duty to utilize the most pertinent researches to bridge theory and practice with coherent and valuable models for the advancement of reading, educational programs, instruction, and assessment.

On the other hand, current research in second language reading has centered on “metacognition.” These studies examine metacognitive awareness of reading techniques and the relationship among recognition of strategies, strategy use, and reading comprehension.

Strategy research proposes that less competent learners may strengthen their abilities through honing in techniques observed by most effective learners.

Relatively, little investigations on metacognitive technique training have been attempted on second or foreign language reading.

Metacognitive reading techniques are conscious means by which students observe their own reading processes including evaluating the effectiveness of cognitive methods being utilized. Metacognitive techniques may include, for instance,

arranging how to approach the reading of a content, testing, and adapting according to purpose and time availability (Devine, 1993). These sorts of methodology might too incorporate Sheory and Mokhtari's (2001) "support strategies" such as the information of how to utilize devices for comprehension such as dictionaries, taking notes or highlighting essential details. If cognitive reading techniques about knowing what method to utilize and how to apply it, then metacognitive strategic knowledge includes understanding the rationale for applying a specific technique in a specific setting, and assessing its importance in terms appropriacy and effectiveness for that setting. Auerbach and Paxton (1997) contend that metacognitive reading can only become efficient when metacognitive techniques, such as working towards a particular objective while reading, are efficiently used.

According to Carrell, Gajdusek and Wise (1998), cases of particular metacognitive techniques in reading may incorporate: setting up goals in reading, evaluating reading materials, repairing miscomprehension, evaluating the ongoing understanding of the text, analyzing the content and paragraph structure to clarify the author's purpose, adjusting reading speed and selective cognitive strategies accordingly, and locks in in self questioning to decide if the goals have been achieved. Hence, reading is a metacognitive, as well as a cognitive process. Whereas cognitive processes refer to purposeful activities that readers take in their efforts to understand texts, metacognitive techniques emphasize the monitoring and regulative mechanisms that readers consciously use to enhance comprehension.

Finally, a major contribution of reading methodologies to fluent reading is their expanding ability as a reader becomes more proficient (Anderson, 2009; Square & Pressley, 2007; Brown & Reynolds, 1999). The general developmental objective to routinize strategic processing still permits a learner to reflect consciously on a technique when required to do so, or when being taught the strategy. However, the

ultimate objective for comprehension techniques is the use of successful methods without persistently requiring to move to a level of conscious problem-solving.

Review of Related Literature

Maqsud (1997) conducted two experiments involving senior high school students in the North-West Province of South Africa to investigate the correlations between metacognitive strategies, nonverbal reasoning ability, and performance in mathematics and English comprehension tests. Analysis of the data revealed significant positive associations between both metacognitive ability and nonverbal reasoning ability with scores in mathematics and English comprehension. Moreover, notable disparities in mathematics performance based on gender were identified. The findings suggest that implementing intervention programs to teach metacognitive strategies to students lacking such skills may enhance their academic achievement.

Pretorius (2002) examined the connection between reading proficiency and academic success at the undergraduate level. The study demonstrated consistent variations in reading proficiency across different academic cohorts, with higher academic groups exhibiting better reading skills. It highlighted significant challenges in reading comprehension among Additional Language (AL) students, indicating limited access to essential declarative knowledge through printed materials in educational contexts. The study underscored the crucial role of reading in facilitating independent access to information and fostering meaningful learning experiences. It emphasized the necessity for developing countries to prioritize the enhancement of students' reading skills and cultivate a culture of reading, emphasizing that reading is not merely an auxiliary skill but the fundamental process through which learning occurs.

Taboada & Rutherford (2011) conducted a formative experiment titled "Developing reading comprehension and academic vocabulary for English language learners through science content" to investigate the impact of two instructional

frameworks on reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, autonomy support perceptions, and reading engagement in fourth-grade English Language Learners (ELLs). The Contextualized Vocabulary Instruction (CVI) framework integrated four reading comprehension strategies with autonomy-supportive motivation practices and implicit instruction of academic science vocabulary. In contrast, the Intensified Vocabulary Instruction (IVI) framework provided explicit instruction of academic science vocabulary alongside autonomy supports. Results showed that the IVI framework led to sustained improvement in students' academic vocabulary even after the intervention ended, while the CVI framework enhanced reading comprehension and perceptions of autonomous learning within the classroom. The findings were interpreted through both quantitative and qualitative lenses within the framework of formative experiments.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

This investigation was grounded in the theories, concepts, principles, and perspectives of experts in reading comprehension skills. Schema theory, outlined by Rumelhart (1980) and further discussed by Carrell & Eisterhold (1981) and Hudson (1982) as cited in An (2013), elucidates how readers utilize prior knowledge to comprehend and learn from text.

According to schema theory, the comprehension of a text involves an interactive process between the reader's background knowledge and the text itself. Efficient comprehension necessitates the ability to connect the textual material with one's own knowledge base. Anderson (1977) emphasizes that every act of comprehension is intertwined with one's understanding of the world. Reading comprehension operates on two fronts: from the bottom up, focusing on specific data from the text, and from the top down, starting with general knowledge to confirm predictions. These two processes, as highlighted by Carrel & Eisterhold (1983) cited

in An (2013), occur simultaneously and interactively, emphasizing the interaction between bottom-up and top-down processes.

Ausubel (1988) posits that for learners to effectively retain and learn new ideas and information, existing knowledge in memory serves as a foundation, providing "ideational anchorage" during the learning process.

The researcher posited that in reading comprehension, as the student engages with the text, they activate, retrieve, associate, correlate, and organize the knowledge already stored in their mind, influencing their cognitive framework to derive meaning from the printed materials. Morrison (1994) asserts that the essence of the reading task lies in deriving appropriate meaning from the text. However, comprehension is not a static skill; it evolves and expands over time, increasingly dependent on the reader's intelligence, background experiences, motivation, interests, and environment.

The study involves two variables, namely: the independent and dependent variables. The independent variable is the reading comprehension skills which include, noting details, getting the meaning of the words, getting the meaning of the phrases, following printed directions, getting meaning of sentence, getting the meaning of paragraph, noting details in selection, perceiving cause-effect, and sequencing events as they happen in the story. The dependent variable includes the scholastic performance of the learners in English.

Figure 1 *The Schema of the Study*

Statement of the Problem

This investigation aimed to find out the effects of metacognitive awareness of senior high school students' reading comprehension in English at Medina College Science High School during the school year 2018-2019.

Specifically, it endeavors to address the following sub-problems:

1. What is the proficiency level of male and female students on the following reading comprehension skills:
 - Noting details in pictures,
 - Getting the meaning of words,
 - Getting the meaning of phrases,
 - Following printed directions,
 - Getting the meaning of sentence,
 - Getting the meaning of paragraphs,
 - Perceiving cause-effect, and
 - Sequencing events as they happen in the story?

2. How different is the male and female students' proficiency level on the aforementioned reading comprehension skills?
3. How is the scholastic performance of the male and female students influenced by metacognitive awareness?
4. What relationship exists between the reading comprehension skills proficiency level and the scholastic performance profiles of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students?

Hypotheses

The following are the null hypotheses to be tested:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the male and female students' proficiency level on the following reading comprehension skills:

- Noting details in pictures,
- Getting the meaning of words,
- Getting the meaning of phrases,
- Following printed directions,
- Getting the meaning of sentence,
- Getting the meaning of paragraphs,
- Perceiving cause-effect, and
- Sequencing events as they happen in the story.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between the reading comprehension skills proficiency level and the scholastic performance of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this investigation may benefit the following persons who are concerned with the school children's development most especially in the area of reading comprehension skills.

- *English Teacher.* The results of this study will be very valuable to the teacher. The data and information gained in this study will provide them some bases for improving students' reading comprehension skills.
- *School Administrator.* The findings of this investigation will provide new directions and insight in assessing the teachers effectively in their supervisory activities.
- *Future Researcher.* The data and information gathered from this investigation may be of value to the educational researcher on reading
- *Reading Specialist.* Relevant methods and techniques will be acquired by the reading specialist in improving children's comprehension abilities.
- *Parents.* The result of this study will serve as bases for parents in following up the reading challenges of their children.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

This investigation covers the metacognitive awareness of senior high school students' reading comprehension in English of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students involved in this study, a total number of 158 individual respondents. This study is confined only in Medina College Science High School in the school year 2018-2019.

Definition of Terms

The following terms are operationally defined and explained for the purposes of clarity and better understanding of the study:

Grade 11 and Grade 12. In the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum of the Philippines, Grade 11 and Grade 12 represent the final two years of senior high school. Grade 11 is typically referred to as the first year of senior high school, while Grade 12 is the second and final year. These two grades are part of the Enhanced Basic Education Program implemented by the Department of Education to align the Philippine educational system with international standards and better prepare students for higher education, employment, or entrepreneurship.

Grade School in the Philippines refers to the elementary level of formal education, typically comprising six years of schooling. It covers Grades 1 to 6 and serves as the foundational stage of the Philippine educational system. Grade School aims to provide students with a basic and comprehensive education, laying the groundwork for further learning and development in higher levels of education. The curriculum encompasses various subjects, including language, mathematics, science, social studies, and values education, designed to promote holistic growth and learning among students. Grade School also emphasizes the acquisition of essential literacy, numeracy, critical thinking, and social skills, preparing students for the challenges of higher education and equipping them with the knowledge and competencies needed for lifelong learning and citizenship.

K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. The K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum in the Philippines is a comprehensive framework implemented by the Department of Education to enhance the country's educational system. Spanning 13 years from Kinder to Grade 12, it emphasizes a holistic approach to education, incorporating spiral progression, specialization tracks, integration of core values, and a focus on 21st century skills. Notable features include the implementation of Mother

Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) and the provision of diverse learning opportunities to prepare students for higher education, employment, or entrepreneurship. Ultimately, the curriculum aims to provide learners with a quality education that fosters critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and digital literacy, ensuring their readiness for success in a globalized world.

Metacognition refers to the cognitive process of awareness and understanding of one's own thinking and learning. It involves the ability to monitor, evaluate, and regulate one's cognitive processes, strategies, and behaviors in order to optimize learning and problem-solving. Metacognition encompasses a range of mental activities, including self-reflection, goal-setting, planning, monitoring progress, and adapting strategies based on feedback and outcomes. Individuals who exhibit strong metacognitive skills are better able to assess their own knowledge and comprehension, identify areas for improvement, and make effective decisions about how to approach learning tasks. Overall, metacognition plays a crucial role in enhancing learning outcomes and fostering lifelong learning and self-directedness.

Metacognitive Awareness refers to an individual's conscious recognition and understanding of their own cognitive processes, strategies, and capabilities. It involves the ability to reflect on one's own thinking, learning, and problem-solving abilities, as well as to recognize and regulate one's cognitive activities. Metacognitive awareness allows individuals to monitor their own comprehension, assess their level of understanding, and adjust their learning strategies accordingly. It involves being aware of one's strengths and weaknesses in cognitive tasks, as well as recognizing when additional effort or a different approach may be necessary to achieve desired learning outcomes. In essence, metacognitive awareness empowers individuals to take control of their own learning processes and become more effective and self-directed learners.

Reading comprehension refers to the ability to understand, interpret, and extract meaning from written texts. It encompasses a multifaceted cognitive process that involves decoding written language, understanding vocabulary and syntax, making inferences, connecting information, and synthesizing ideas. Effective reading comprehension involves not only understanding the literal meaning of the text but also grasping its deeper implications, context, and underlying themes. It is a fundamental skill essential for academic success, critical thinking, and information processing across various disciplines and contexts.

Science High School. A Science High School in the Philippines is a specialized secondary educational institution that focuses on providing rigorous and intensive instruction in the fields of science, mathematics, and technology. These schools aim to identify and nurture academically talented and highly motivated students with a keen interest in scientific inquiry and exploration. Admission to Science High Schools is typically based on competitive entrance examinations and academic performance. Students enrolled in Science High Schools undergo a specialized curriculum that emphasizes advanced coursework in science, mathematics, and related disciplines, along with laboratory work, research projects, and extracurricular activities aimed at developing critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and scientific literacy. Science High Schools play a crucial role in nurturing the next generation of scientists, engineers, and innovators, preparing them for higher education and careers in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields, as well as contributing to the advancement of science and technology in the Philippines.

Senior High School (SHS) in the Philippines refers to the program which is the last two years of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, following the completion of Junior High School (Grades 7-10). Implemented by the Department of Education (DepEd), Senior High School aims to provide students with additional specialized knowledge and skills to better prepare them for higher education,

employment, or entrepreneurship. SHS offers various specialized tracks, including academic, technical-vocational, arts and design, and sports tracks, allowing students to choose a path aligned with their interests and career aspirations. The curriculum emphasizes both academic and practical learning, incorporating hands-on experiences, work immersion, and opportunities for career exploration and development. Senior High School plays a crucial role in equipping Filipino students with the competencies and capabilities needed to succeed in the 21st century workforce and contribute to the country's socio-economic development.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive survey approach was employed to address the central inquiries and ancillary questions of this study. The endeavors primarily entailed employing quantitative techniques to delineate the general characteristics of the group under examination.

Descriptive research defies strict categorization into either quantitative or qualitative methodologies; rather, it often incorporates aspects of both within a single study. The term "descriptive research" pertains to the research question, design, and data analysis methods applied to a particular subject. While descriptive statistics reveal what exists, inferential statistics seek to ascertain causality.

Descriptive research entails the collection of data that describes events, followed by organization, tabulation, visualization, and presentation of the gathered data (Glass & Hopkins, 1984). It frequently employs visual aids such as graphs and charts to facilitate comprehension of data distribution. Given the human mind's limitations in processing vast amounts of raw data, descriptive statistics play a crucial role in condensing data into a manageable format. In instances where detailed narrative descriptions of a small number of cases are involved, description serves as a tool to structure data into discernible patterns that emerge during analysis. These patterns aid in understanding the implications of a qualitative study.

Research Environment

Medina College Science High School is the junior and senior high school department of the Medina College institution in Ozamiz City, Philippines. Medina College is a private, non-sectarian institution of basic and higher learning founded by a group of civic-minded professionals.

In the spirit of service, the institution aims to break down the financial barriers to accessing the highest standards in education to enable more Filipino

families to send their children up to college. It also envisions its students to reach beyond themselves and expand their horizons, thus, equipping them to face life's challenges ahead.

Research Respondents

There were 158 Grade 11 and Grade 12 (senior high school) students officially enrolled in Medina College Science High School, composed of 80 males and 78 females.

Distribution Procedure

The lottery sampling was employed in selecting the representative of the study by section. The procedures were first, by assigning numbers to the participants of the population, assembling them in a sample form, wrote the numbers on small pieces of paper. Next, rolled the small pieces of papers and placed in a container big enough to allow them to roll and move freely in all directions. After shaking the container well, the desired number of participants were picked out and served as the sample.

Research Instruments

The researcher, under the guidance of the thesis adviser, prepared diagnostic test questions based on the K to 12 curriculum for the grade levels. The table of specification served as the guide in the preparation of the instrument. The dummy of the instrument was submitted to the thesis committee for correction, evaluation and approval.

Instrument Validity

After the preliminary corrections of the instrument. It was organized and prepared ready for the dry-run. It was tried out among the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students in Clarin National High School, a public school in the neighboring town.

The purpose of the validation was to determine whether the test questions are valid, reliable and acceptable. The result of the validation are not included in the

final thesis but are kept confidential and made the basis for enriching the instrument.

The researcher again submitted the result of the trial dry-run together with the instrument to the thesis committee for final refinement and validation.

Scoring of the Instrument

The researcher hand scored the test papers of the students tested to avoid unintentional problems. The results of the tests were submitted to the statistician through the research adviser for statistical treatment of the collected data.

The arbitrarily established continuum for quantitative interpretations of the data with their corresponding descriptive rating is presented:

Point Scales

Descriptive Ratings

30 – 37

Superior (S)

23 – 29.99

Above Average (AA)

16 – 22.99

Average (A)

9 – 15.99

Below Average (BA)

1 – 8.99

Inferior (I)

6 Point Scales

Descriptive Ratings

5.00 – 6.00

Superior (S)

4.00 – 4.99

Above Average (AA)

3.00 – 3.99

Average (A)

2.00 – 2.99

Below Average (BA)

1.00 – 1.99

Inferior (I)

5 Point Scales

Descriptive Ratings

4.21 – 5.00

Superior (S)

3.42 – 4.20	Above Average (AA)
2.61 – 3.40	Average (A)
1.81 – 2.60	Below Average (BA)
1.00 – 1.80	Inferior (I)

4 Point Scales**Descriptive Ratings**

3.30 – 4.00	Superior (S)
2.60 – 3.29	Above Average (AA)
1.90 – 2.59	Average (A)
1.20 – 1.89	Below Average (BA)
0.50 – 1.19	Inferior (I)

3 Point Scales**Descriptive Ratings**

2.50 – 3.00	Superior (S)
2.00 – 2.49	Above Average (AA)
1.50 – 1.99	Average (A)
1.00 – 1.49	Below Average (BA)
0.50 – 0.99	Inferior (I)

6 Point Scales**Descriptive Ratings**

95 – 100%	Outstanding (O)
85 – 94.99%	Very Satisfactory (VS)
75 – 84.99%	Satisfactory (S)
65 – 74.99%	Moderately Satisfactory (MS)
Below 65%	Needs Improvement (NI)

Ethical Considerations

For ethical reasons, the respondents were informed and briefed about the purpose and objectives of this study. Moreover, they were informed that they could withdraw their participation at any time they would want. Their personal information were secured with confidentiality and anonymity. The respondents had answered the evaluation in their own volition. Any mode of resistance by the respondent was highly respected.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher asked permission from the school president by sending a letter channeled through the vice president for academic affairs and basic education principal. This was done for the researcher to secure a permit to conduct a survey on the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students. After the approval of the request, the initial data gathering commenced.

Statistical Treatment

The following tools utilized in the treatment of the data in order to come up with the analysis to answer the major and specific questions and to test the hypotheses of the study:

- *Mean.* This tool was used in the computation of the arithmetic means in each type of test in reading comprehension skills and to determine the proficiency of the students.

The formula was as follows:

$$X = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

Where:

X	=	mean
$\sum x$	=	summation of scores
N	=	number of cases

- *z-test*. This tool was used to find the difference between categories and to determine whether the reading comprehension skills proficiency levels of the two groups differ significantly.

The formula was as follows:

$$z = \frac{x_1 - x_2}{\sqrt{\frac{s_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{s_2^2}{n_2}}}$$

Where:

z = z-test of significance

$x_1 \& 2$ = mean of the first and second group

$s_1 \& 2$ = standard deviation of the first and second group

$n_1 \& 2$ = number of cases of the first and second group

- *Pearson r Product-Moment Coefficient of Correlation*. This statistical tool was used to find out if there existed a relationship between the proficiency level on reading comprehension skills and scholastic performance profile of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students.

The formula was as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2 \quad n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}$$

Where:

r_{xy} = Pearson Product-Moment Correlation

n = number of cases

x = first variable

y = second variable

In testing the significance of r , the t -test was used with the formula:

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$$

Where:

t = t -value

r = r -value

n = number of cases

All statistical tests are set at .05 level of significance.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Overview

The detailed presentation, interpretation and analyses of the data gathered through the self-made instrument administered to the subject-respondents are found in this chapter.

No matter how much effort is exerted by the teachers in developing the reading comprehension skills of the learners, there are children who could never master the skills, the factors interfering with comprehension are limited intelligence, insufficient familiarity with the basic concepts of the subject matter, and lack of interest in the material.

Male Students Proficiency Level

Table 1 reflects the proficiency levels of male students on the reading comprehension skills.

Table 1 *Proficiency Level of the Male Students on the Metacognitive Reading Comprehension Skills*

Skills	HPS	HSO	LSO	X	X%	SD	DR/ DL	R
Noting details in pictures	3	3	1	2.18	79.3	.567	AA	1
Getting the meaning of words	5	5	0	1.42	50.4	.500	BA	8
Getting the meaning of phrases	3	3	0	1.99	66.3	.474	A	4
Following printed directions	3	3	1	2.13	71.0	.507	AA	3
Getting the meaning of sentences	3	3	0	2.14	71.3	.510	AA	2
Getting the meaning of paragraph	4	4	1	1.55	56.3	.540	A	7
Noting the details in selection	6	6	1	1.75	57.5	.821	A	6
Perceiving cause and effect	4	4	0	1.53	48.8	.464	A	9

Sequencing events as they happen in the story	6	6	1	1.84	64.0	.914	A	5
Average				1.83	61.2	.539	A	

Legend:

HPS	=	Highest possible score
HSO	=	Highest score obtained
LSO	=	Lowest score obtained
X	=	Mean
SD	=	Standard deviation
DR	=	Descriptive rating
PL	=	Proficiency level
R	=	Rank

Noting details obtained a computed mean of 2.18 or 79.3% which is equivalent to a descriptive rating of above average (AA) proficiency level and ranked number 1.

Getting the meaning of words gathered a computed mean of 1.42 or 50.4% out of five test items which is equivalent to a descriptive rating of below average (BA) proficiency level and ranked number 8.

Getting the meaning of phrases got a computed mean of 1.99 or 66.3% out of three test items which is has a descriptive rating of average (A) proficiency level and ranked 4.

Following printed directions obtained a computed mean of 2.13 or 71% out of three test items which is equivalent to a descriptive rating of above average (AA) proficiency level and ranked number 3.

Getting the meaning of sentences obtained a computed mean of 2.14 or 71.3% out of three test items which is equivalent to a descriptive rating of above average proficiency level.

Getting the meaning of paragraph with a computed mean of 1.55 or 56.3% out of four test items is equal to a qualitative rating of average proficiency level and ranked number 7.

Noting details in selection with a computed mean of 1.75 or 57.5% out of six test items is equal to a descriptive rating of average proficiency level and ranked number 6.

Perceives cause and effect with a mean of 1.53 or 48.8% out of four test items is average proficiency level and ranked number 9.

Sequences events as they happen in the story obtained a mean of 1.84 or 64% out of six test items is average proficiency level and ranked number 5.

A closer look at the Table 1 revealed that three (3) items in reading comprehension skills included in the study were found to be AA. These were noting details in picture, following printed directions, and getting the meaning of the sentence. These were supported with the means of 2.18, 2.14, and 2.13 respectively. This implies that the male students have adequate or sufficient competence on the mentioned skills.

In an unstructured interview conducted by the researcher to the students concerned, they revealed that these three skills were very easy to be understood because of the guide pictures, printed directions, and the sentences which were given. Moreover, the teachers have also very good performance in imparting the lesson to them.

Five items, namely, getting the meaning of phrases, getting the meaning of the paragraph, noting details in the selection, perceiving cause and effect, and sequencing the events as they happen in the story were revealed as A. This means that the students had acquired just only a mediocre performance.

Male students revealed that these skills were quite complicated and could not be absorbed to their minds if there were no guide at all. Though their teachers performed well in the explanation, but sad to say, when the examination came, they only got average proficiency level.

Lastly, the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students have found difficulty in getting the meaning of words. Their proficiency level on the said skill was BA. This means that the students were not proficient enough in the skill. There was a need for them to be guided by their teachers in such manner to increase their performance.

As a whole, the Grade 11 and Grade 12 male students obtained the average weighted mean of 1.83 with a standard deviation of 5.397, which falls on the average or satisfactory proficiency level in reading comprehension skills.

Female Students Proficiency Level

Table 2 presents the proficiency levels of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 female students on the reading comprehension skills.

Table 2 *Proficiency Level of the Female Students on the Metacognitive Reading Comprehension Skills*

Skills	HPS	HSO	LSO	X	X%	SD	DR/ DL	R
Noting details in pictures	3	3	1	2.93	79.3	.567	AA	1
Getting the meaning of words	5	5	0	1.97	50.4	.500	A	7
Getting the meaning of phrases	3	3	0	2.00	66.3	.474	A	6
Following printed directions	3	3	1	2.42	71.0	.507	AA	3
Getting the meaning of sentences	3	3	0	2.00	71.3	.510	AA	5
Getting the meaning of paragraph	4	4	1	2.73	56.3	.540	AA	2
Noting the details in selection	6	6	1	1.90	57.5	.821	AA	8
Perceiving cause and effect	4	4	0	1.54	48.8	.464	A	9
Sequencing events as they happen in the story	6	6	1	2.12	64.0	.914	A	4
Average				2.18	61.2	.539	AA	

Legend:

HPS	=	Highest possible score
HSO	=	Highest score obtained
LSO	=	Lowest score obtained
X	=	Mean
SD	=	Standard deviation
DR	=	Descriptive rating
PL	=	Proficiency level
R	=	Rank

Noting details obtained a computed mean of 2.93 with the standard deviation of .555 which is rated above average proficiency level and ranked number 1.

Getting the meaning of words garnered a computed mean of 1.97 bearing a standard deviation of .658 which means an average proficiency level and ranked number 7.

Getting the meaning of phrases got a mean of 2.00 with .476 SD, which equates to average proficiency level and ranked number 6.

Following printed directions obtained a computed mean of 2.42 with .576 SD, which equates to above average proficiency level and ranked number 3.

Getting the meaning of sentences obtained a computed mean of 2.00 and .480 SD, which equates to above average proficiency level and ranked number 5.

Getting the meaning of the paragraphs obtained a computed mean of 2.73 and .650 SD, which equates to above average proficiency level and ranked number 2.

Noting details in the selection obtained a computed mean of 1.90 and .927 SD, which equates to average proficiency level and ranked number 8.

Perceiving cause and effect obtained a computed mean of 2.12 and .485 SD, which equates to average proficiency level and ranked number 9.

Sequencing events as they happen in the story obtained a computed mean of 2.12 and .976 SD, which equates to above average proficiency level and ranked number 4.

As analyzed, the Grade 11 and Grade 12 female students showed better performance in noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of phrases, following

printed directions, getting the meaning of the paragraph, and sequencing events as they happen in the story, where they got above average (AA) proficiency level. This indicates that females had shown a very satisfactory performance in reading comprehension skills.

However, the female students scored average proficiency level in getting the meaning of words, getting details in selections, and perceiving cause and effect relationship. This implies that the proficiency levels of the female students are in need to exposed in various exercises to master these skills.

In totality, the average weighted mean of the nine reading comprehension skills obtained by the female students was 2.18, bearing a 5.786 SD, is rated as above average (AA) proficiency level. This implies that the female students exceeded the expected performance and better than the male counterparts in language or reading comprehension skills.

Consolidation of Results

Many factors have contributed to the low performance in reading comprehension for students (Sanford, 2015). One of the major factors that causes reading comprehension difficulty is the lack of prior knowledge, this idea is advanced by a number process, this means that anchorage failure of the reader to activate prior knowledge to fill the gaps in the interaction with the materials. Such interpretation of the text will result in hampering comprehension.

In the investigation, the researcher tested the significance of the difference between the proficiency levels of the male and female students on the reading comprehension skills presented in Table 3.

Table 3 *Test on Significant Difference between the Proficiency Levels of the Male and Female Students in the Reading Comprehension Skills*

Skills	Means		XD	Z
	M = 80	F = 78		
Noting details in pictures	2.18	1.98	.75	3.7160*

Getting the meaning of words	1.42	1.97	.55	2.9950**
Getting the meaning of phrases	1.99	2.00	.01	0.1622*
Following printed directions	2.13	2.42	.29	4.1200*
Getting the meaning of sentences	2.14	2.00	.14	2.0570**
Getting the meaning of paragraph	1.55	2.73	.15	5.1740*
Noting the details in selection	1.75	1.90	1.23	2.7930*
Perceiving cause and effect	1.53	1.54	.01	1.3800**
Sequencing events as they happen in the story	1.84	2.12	0.28	2.2200*

Legend:

M	=	Male
F	=	Female
XD	=	Mean difference
Z	=	z-value
*	=	Significant
**	=	Not significant

Noting details has a mean difference of .75 which existed between the proficiency levels of the male and female students on the reading comprehension skills and score a z-value of 3.716. The difference is significant, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. Male and female proficiency level in noting details from pictures were not similar. Females seem to perform better than males in noting details from pictures.

Getting the meaning of words has a mean difference of .55 and z-value of 2.995, thus displays a significant difference. This implies that females are more proficient in getting the meaning of words than males.

Getting the meaning of phrases has a mean difference of .01 and z-value of .0162, which means that the difference is not significant. This implies that male and females both can perform well in this reading comprehension skill.

Following printed directions obtained a mean difference of .29 between the proficiency level of the male and female students on this reading comprehension

skill. The z-test registered a z-value of 4.12 which means that both respondents showed diverse performance in following printed directions. Hence, in this competency, females perform better than males.

Getting the meaning of sentences obtained a mean difference of 0.14 and z-value of 2.05 between the proficiency levels of the male and female. This means that the male and female respondents have differing proficiency levels in getting the meaning of sentences. Thus, this shows that males perform better than females in getting the meaning of sentences reading comprehension skill.

Getting the meaning of paragraph obtained a mean difference of 1.23 and z-value of 6.17 between the male and female groups. This means that one of the groups performed better than the other, hence, females excel in this reading comprehension skill over their male counterparts.

Perceiving cause and effect obtained a mean difference of .01 and z-value of 1.38. This means that there is no significant difference between the male and female performances in this reading comprehension skill. Thus, males and females have similar performance in perceiving cause and effect in texts.

Sequencing events as they happen in the story obtained a mean difference of .28 and z-value of 1.96. This illustrates a significance difference between the performances of the male and female respondents. Thus, this presents that the female students are better in sequencing events as they happen in the story than the male students.

As a whole, out of the nine reading comprehension skills treated, seven of them different significantly from one another, namely, these skills are: noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of words, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentences, getting the meaning of paragraph, noting details in selections, and sequencing events in the story as they happen. Getting the meaning of words, getting the meaning of phrases, and perceiving cause and effects showed no

significant difference between the male and female participants. In this study, females seem to show better performances than males in most of the reading comprehension skills.

Proficiency in reading serves as a fundamental pathway to achievement across academic disciplines. In contemporary society, the capacity to comprehend effectively is paramount for learning. Reading encompasses cognitive, emotional, and societal dimensions, constituting a crucial aspect of a child's growth with far-reaching effects on personal, social, and mental well-being (Aquino & De Vera, 2018).

Considering the various influences contributing to the challenges faced by learners in reading over the last two decades, effective teaching emerges as a primary solution for assisting children. Direct instruction in essential academic skills such as reading, writing, and arithmetic, commonly referred to as the 3R's, proves largely effective. Therefore, the classroom teacher plays a pivotal role in identifying issues among students (Nyarko et al., 2018).

Table 4 shows the comparative scholastic performance of the male and female students. The data shows that the female students obtained a performance rating of 80.08 percent which is comparatively higher than the male students which is 76.60 percent. However, both groups have equal descriptive rating or performance which is "satisfactory" (S).

Table 4 *Comparative Scholastic Performance of the Male and Female Students*

Sex	N	PR	PP	R
Male	80	76.60 %	S	2
Female	78	80.08 %	S	1
Overall	158	79.88 %	S	

Legend:

- N = number of cases
- PR = performance rating
- PP = performance profile
- R = rank

<i>Scales</i>		<i>Descriptive Rating</i>
95-100 %	=	Outstanding (O)
85-94 %	=	Very Satisfactory (VS)
75-84 %	=	Satisfactory (S)
65-71 %	=	Moderately Satisfactory (MS)
Below 65 %	=	Needs Improvement (NI)

Students have varied needs for reading. The several needs are the same for all, differing only in degree depending upon the maturity of the individuals. In general, reading gives the students the ability to live a richer, fuller and more complete life. It was hypothesized that there was no significant relationship between the metacognitive skills proficiency level and the scholastic performance of the students, however, that is rejected in this study.

Table 5 indicates the relationship between the metacognitive skills proficiency levels and the scholastic performance of the G11 and Grade 12 students.

Table 5 *Relationship between Metacognitive Skills Proficiency Level and Scholastic Performance of the Students*

Variables	N	R	df	α	CV	T
X	158	.16	147	.05	1.96	2.8616
Y	158					

Legend:

X	=	proficiency levels
Y	=	scholastic performance
N	=	number of cases
R	=	coefficient of correlation
df	=	degree of freedom
α	=	level of significance
CV	=	critical value

There is a .16 correlation value between the metacognitive skills and the scholastic performance of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students. This suggests that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. The t-test analysis registered a computed value of 2.86, which is greater than the tabular value of 1.96 at .05 level of significance with 147 degrees of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Results imply that the students should be given more practice exercises on reading comprehension skills employing metacognitive awareness. This implies, further, that the scholastic performance is affected by the student's ability to comprehend the materials read. The better the reading comprehension skills, the better the scholastic performance.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The proficiency levels of the male students on the metacognitive skills in reading comprehension were found to be “average” in noting details in pictures, following printed directions, and getting the meaning of the paragraph. All the other skills, namely, getting the meaning of words, getting the meaning of phrases, getting the meaning of sentences, noting details in the selection, perceiving cause and effect, and sequencing events in the story, were found to be “below average.”

Moreover, it was found out that female students obtained “above average” on the following skills: noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of phrases, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentences, getting the meaning of the paragraph, and sequencing events in the story. Additionally, female students obtained “average” proficiency level in getting the meaning of the words, noting details in the selection, and perceiving cause and effect.

There is a significant difference between the male and female students’ proficiency level in metacognitive skills along noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of words, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentences, getting the meaning of paragraphs, noting details in the selection, and sequencing events in the story. While, in getting the meaning of phrases and perceiving cause and effect bear no significant comparative difference between the proficiency levels of male and female students. In entirety, there is a significant relationship between the male and female students’ proficiency level in metacognitive reading comprehension skills.

The scholastic performance of both the male and female Grade 11 and Grade 12 students was found to be “satisfactory.” This means that they were not quite outstanding nor underperforming.

There is a significant positive correlation between the metacognitive skills in reading comprehension and the scholastic performance of the students. This seems to be the higher the students' metacognitive proficiency level in reading comprehension, the more likely they will perform better academically.

Conclusion

In the light of the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The female students are more likely to better employ most metacognitive skills in reading comprehension than the male students.

Furthermore, the female students are more superior than the male students in various metacognitive strategies in reading comprehension, particularly, in the aspects of noting details in pictures, getting the meaning of phrases, following printed directions, getting the meaning of sentences, getting the meaning of the paragraph, and sequencing events in the story.

Additionally, furthermore, despite rating an above average reading comprehension proficiency for females and average for males, students only a satisfactory rating in their scholastic performance across various school subjects.

Lastly, it is very important to take note that, as the data suggest, the higher the proficiency level of the students in employing metacognitive awareness in reading comprehension skills, the greater the students will academically perform in school.

Recommendations

In view of the data and findings of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

The above average proficiency levels of the male students on the reading comprehension skills should be sustained, the average level should be reinforced and upgraded, and the below average should be given more attention by the school administrators and the teachers.

The above proficiency levels of the female students on the metacognitive skills should be enriched and the average proficiency should be carefully studied by the teachers so that relevant steps could be instituted for the benefits of the students.

The no significant difference between the reading comprehension skills should be analytically studied by the teachers so they could recommend measures for the welfare of the students. While the significant difference of the proficiency levels between the male and female students should be given more provisions by giving tailored activities on the subject areas for the advantages of the students.

The satisfactory performance profiles of the male and female Grade 11 and Grade 12 students should be given more attention by the teachers so they could provide effective measures to improve students' performance in the classroom. The teachers should utilize varied and appropriate strategies and techniques in teaching in the subject areas for the advantages of the clientele.

The significant relationship between the metacognitive skills proficiency level and the scholastic performance profile of the Grade 11 and Grade 12 students should be examined carefully by the teachers so that relevant provisions could be introduced for the upgrading of students' proficiency levels on reading comprehension skills which would help improve and enrich further the students' scholastic performance profiles.

Moreover, teachers should be required to read and subscribe on professional books, magazines, journals, periodicals, and other source materials in reading for the benefits of the students in particular and teachers in general.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher deeply expresses with profound gratitude and sincere appreciation to the following persons who in one way or another extended their assistance.

To all the members of the panel for sharing their ideas and giving constructive criticism during the oral examination leading to the improvement and refinement of this work.

Above all, to our God Almighty, the author of supreme knowledge and wisdom, for giving the researcher the strength and provision to finish the study.

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